

CHALLENGES, STRATEGIES, AND THE LEVEL OF PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS: INPUTS FOR A PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT PLAN

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ABSTRACT

Educators encounter multifaceted challenges brought by external and internal factors that affect their delivery of instruction. This Exploratory-sequential study sought to understand the challenges encountered by Senior High School teachers in Lesson Planning, Implementation and Feedback, Strategies they employ, and the level of pedagogical content knowledge of teachers as assessed by students. Using a Semi-Structured Interview, 10 teachers were divided into two Focus Group discussions that deal with their experiences and challenges in teaching. While 324 students were asked to answer a 7-point Researcher-made survey questionnaire. Results shows that educators encountered “Learning Gap”, Challenges in administering “Ready-made WLP”, Challenges in “Handling Student Behavior”, “Addressing Students’ Mental Health Issues”, “Mismatch of subject taught”, “Student Reception of Feedback”, “Designing activities to cater diverse needs of students”, and “Limited time” in teaching. Moreover, Teachers overcome these challenges by employing innovative “Strategies in Planning the lesson”, “Adjustment Approaches” and additional “Strategies in ensuring that students achieve performance indicators”. Subsequently, students “Agree” (5.31 Mean Score) to their teachers Lesson Planning, “Somewhat Agree” to Implementation and Feedback (5.29, 5.22 Mean Score respectively). The results imply that despite challenges encountered, teachers were able to address any hindrances by employing innovative strategies. This study recommends conducting Professional Development Programs to manage and provide technical assistance for teachers.

Keywords: *Challenges, Strategies, Pedagogical Content Knowledge*

INTRODUCTION

The teaching profession is always regarded as the noblest profession due to its enduring role in the development of a child and nation building. Despite this high regard, it is undeniable that teachers face notable external and internal challenges in the profession that may hamper their performance in the teaching and learning process. The nature of a teacher's work encompasses the corners of their classroom due to their roles in supporting and bridging the communities they belong. According to Ogundare et al., (2023) teachers – specially those working in a private institution experienced significant challenges compared to those employed with public institutions.

In the Philippines, private school teachers encounter numerous workload-related challenges, including finding work-life balance, managing student behaviors, and adjusting to class preparations (Legaspi & Fernandez, 2022). There is an increased demand on teachers' workload in the advent of the COVID-19 Pandemic that requires teachers to demonstrate resilience in adversities and adapt to the new teaching landscapes (Banal & Cruz, 2022). Azado (2023) emphasized that the lack of relevant measures to address these challenges can contribute to difficulties in retaining teachers in private school settings. Hence, it is important for researchers to analyze challenges encountered by teachers in private schools and propose solution to combat it.

In addition, private school teachers often have more pressures such as job insecurity, low wages relative to their counterparts in public schools and no institutional support. Consequently, these factors contribute to higher levels of stress and burnout which can ultimately affect teacher retention rates. This makes it important to note the importance of targeted measures to put in place to address this challenge.

There are several reasons why we should recognize and address these challenges. Understanding the unique difficulties that private school teachers face may lead to the development of focused support mechanisms that improve their professional well-being and efficacy. Examining these challenges exposes systemic problems within education systems that need attention for improved educational outcomes across the board. These challenges provide a basis for researchers and policymakers interested in designing complete professional development plans that equip teachers with the necessary abilities, materials, and assistance they will need while working out their roles effectively.

Though teaching is highly regarded for its noble cause, it is faced with countless problems that could possibly hinder educators' performance in their respective duties. Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK) is a critical component in addressing challenges encountered by teachers. PCK refers to the knowledge that an educator possess that enables them to deliver content to student in a comprehensible manner (Mthethwa-Kunene et al., 2015) Hence, it is noteworthy that teachers can overcome these by implementing various strategies. This also includes Teachers' content mastery in teaching learners as it is underpinned by its effect in instructional quality and student

development (Kunter et al., 2013). Teachers Mastery plays a critical role in shaping learning experiences and outcomes among students. Turocy (2015) argued that teacher's expertise and mastery of teachers implies a significant impact to student learning.

Consequently, the significance and implications of pedagogical content knowledge in addressing challenges within the teaching and learning process becomes apparent. Such teachers are more likely to promote students' conceptual understanding; cater for their diverse learning needs, present subject matter effectively; and improve student achievement overall. Its usefulness in preparing a learning atmosphere that is more apt at bringing the student's cognition and collaboration together can result when provided along with content understanding using suitable training techniques.

This research sought to understand the challenges, strategies employed and the level of pedagogical content knowledge of teachers in teaching. By scrutinizing these techniques and obstacles, this research aimed to create a comprehensive Professional Development Plan that is tailored to address each challenge faced by teachers in a private institution.

Research Objectives

This study sought to understand the experiences of teachers in a private school in teaching and how their students assess their pedagogical content knowledge. Specifically, this study sought to uncover the following research objectives:

1. Determine the Challenges encountered by teachers in Teaching.
2. Determine the strategies employed by teachers in addressing challenges.
3. Determine the student assessment of teachers' pedagogical content knowledge in terms of:
 - a. Lesson Planning
 - b. Implementation
 - c. Feedback

Moreover, the researchers assumed that: (1) Teachers encounter challenges in student behavior and attitudes; (2) Teachers encounter challenges in handling diversity of learners; (3) Teachers encounter difficulties in forming constructive feedback; (4) Teachers encounter challenges in addressing student's gaps in learning; (5) Teachers adjust their lesson to address diversity of learners, student behavior and attitudes; and (6) Teachers employ innovative strategies in addressing various student needs.

METHODOLOGY

This part presents the pertinent methodologies used to carry out this study. This includes the Research design, Key Informants, Data Gathering Procedure and Data Analysis.

Research Design

The research design for this study adopts an exploratory-sequential approach, integrating both qualitative and quantitative in two consecutive phases. This design allows for a comprehensive exploration of a research topic by utilizing both qualitative and quantitative methods in a sequential manner (Akçay & Avci, 2022). Narrative Inquiry is adapted to uncover the challenges and strategies of teachers and in the Quantitative Phase, a descriptive design is used to describe students' assessment of teachers' pedagogical content knowledge.

Key Informants and Respondents of the study

The researchers gathered Qualitative data from the experiences, challenges, and strategies employed by 10 Senior High School Teachers, which were divided into two Focus Group Discussions. Meanwhile, a sample of 324 students from various strands was selected to answer a researcher-made survey questionnaire using Stratified Sampling.

Data Gathering Procedure

In the nature of this study, the researcher used a semi-structured interview method with two focus groups, each consisting of five teachers. These interviews were conducted to explore their views and were recorded through voice recorder, which allowed for accurate recording of responses. At the same time, the researcher took extensive notes during the interviews to capture nuances and potential recurring themes. The recorded data were securely stored in an online repository and could only be accessed through encrypted passwords to ensure confidentiality and data integrity. The audio recordings were then transcribed verbatim, and the transcripts were formally organized to identify emerging themes and patterns to expand our understanding and gain insights from different perspectives, online documents, shared via their respective messenger group chats, were safely stored on the drive. Upon completion of the data collection and analysis phase, raw data were immediately deleted in support of confidentiality standards and in compliance with ethical guidelines. This comprehensive design of data collection resulted in research questions that were rigorously tested and complete and contributed to the robustness of our findings.

Data Analysis

This research utilized Thematic Analysis to process qualitative data gathered from two Focus Group Discussions. Creswell (2014) defined this analysis as a systematic process for coding data in which specific statements are analyzed and categorized into themes that represent the phenomenon of interest. Meanwhile, Mean and Standard Deviation was used to analyze the answers of the respondents from a 7-point survey questionnaire.

RESULTS

Figure 1. *The Challenges Encountered by Teachers in Teaching*

Teachers play a crucial role in shaping the academic and personal development of their students (Gupta, 2023). However, they often face numerous challenges that can impact their ability to effectively deliver instruction and support student learning. The result shows the various challenges encountered by teachers, including “learning gaps”, “ready-made weekly Lesson Plan (WLP)”, “handling student behavior”, “addressing student mental health issues”, “student reception of feedback”, “subject mismatch”, “limited time”, and “designing activities to cater to diverse student needs”.

One of the themes identified in the study is “*Utilizing ready-made WLP*” as part of the challenges encountered by teachers. This theme is shown on the verbatim of Teacher B1 stated that “*nakakaencouter ako ng difficulty in following standard WLP kasi minsan yung standard WLP ay hindi akma sa teaching style ko.*” This verbatim is supported by Teacher A3 stating, “*May mga activities na hindi perfectly nakaalign kay WLP at sa needs ng students or sa specific learning objectives na nagiging challenge sa teacher para i-adapt yung WLP.*” The verbatim shows that teachers who are not capable of teaching the subject find a hard time adapting to the departmentalized WLL.

This statement of the key informants leads to “subject mismatch”. Teacher B5 stated “*may mga teachers na nabigyan ng subject which is not align with their major na kinuha nung college ayun nahihirapan silang ituro yung subject.*” The statement of the key informants is evident as well in the local study conducted to Samson (2017), which revealed that in MSU-Maguindanao, the English writing proficiency of the Maguindanao college students is deficient. This deficiency is caused by varied factors including English teachers’ practices reflecting a lack of pedagogical knowledge because of a mismatch in teachers’ qualifications and the subject taught.

Subject mismatch becomes one factor that contributes to the learning gap of the students. According to Vietnam Teaching Jobs (2023), one of the primary challenges faced by teachers is the presence of learning gaps among students. This is evident in the statement of Teacher B2 stating, “*May mga ano po kasi na kailangan yung bata bago makalevel ng [lesson] parang alam muna nila yung mga basic pero yung ibang bata po since hindi po nila alam yon... nag aadjust po yung teachers sa [understanding] ng bata. Imbis na makakapag move na kami sa next lesson kailangan pa po naming idiscuss yung mga basic na dapat alam na. ‘yung iba po talaga is hindi po talaga nila alam. So kami po, mag didiscuss po kami non bago po umpisahan namin yung discussion namin which is nagkakaron po talaga ng problem.*” This verbatim shows that teachers need to teach the basic concepts of the subject before they are going to deal with the complex topics, which should be the targeted lesson inside the curriculum guide. Teacher A3 reiterated that going back to the basics makes the students understand the lesson. Teacher A3 added that if the teachers do not go back to the basic concepts, it would be difficult for students to grasp the topic.

Time constraints within the academic schedule can pose significant challenges for teachers in covering curriculum content thoroughly, providing meaningful feedback to students, and addressing individual learning needs adequately. This is evident in the statement of Teacher B3 stating, “*Ito yung topic that day pero may times na hindi natin sya na totopic kasi minsan merong suspension of classes*” It is also supported by teacher B4’s verbatim stating “*Kung baga nagiging maigsi yung time natin para idiscuss yung lesson so ang ginagawa natin naghahabol tayo ng lesson. So ang nangyayari kapag naghahabol tayo ng lesson hindi natin masyado na i-didiscuss o naelaborate yung mga lessons.*” This is also evident in the study cited by Javier (2022), that the teachers have also encountered challenges like the inability to accommodate all learning concerns due to limited time, and learning gaps in the subject of reading and writing. This is aligned with

the formulated theme that teachers encounter challenges in addressing student's gaps in learning.

Furthermore, teachers are having a hard time formulating an activity that will cater diverse needs of students. Difficulty in catering diverse needs of students is evident in teachers A4 and B2 stating that *“mahirap mag gawa ng activities sa math na mag fi-fit sa iba't-ibang klase ng mga estudyante”*. The two key informants are having a hard time designing activities in mathematics that will suit diverse students because students' needs vary, and they need to go back to the basic concept for them to teach the intended learning outcome for the lesson. Because of the diversity of students, teachers are having challenges in handling student behavior. As stated by teachers A1, A3, A4, A5, and teachers B3, B4, and B5, the student's behavior of this generation is different from others because sometimes they misbehave. These narratives are aligned with the formulated assumption that teachers encounter challenges in student behavior and attitudes and teachers encounter challenges in handling diversity of learners.

It also shows that teachers are having challenges in addressing student mental health issues. As stated by teacher B1, *“actually po, hindi ko po alam kung paano ihahandle yung mga students na may mental health issues”*. Teachers B2, B3, B4, and B5 agreed on the statement of teacher B1. Teacher B1 added that *“Sorry to say this po, pero sadly may mga teachers po na insensitive sa feelings ng ibang mga estudyante”*. Teachers may face the responsibility of identifying and supporting students experiencing mental health challenges, such as anxiety or depression, which can impact their academic performance and the overall well-being of the students.

Providing constructive feedback is essential for student growth, but teachers encounter challenges like students being resistant to feedback or struggling to understand and apply it effectively in their learning process. As stated by the key informants, teachers do not know how they are going to deliver feedback in a way that students will not see it in a negative way. This is aligned with the formulated theme that teachers encounter difficulties in forming constructive feedback.

Figure 2. Strategies employed by Teachers to Address Challenges

Teachers frequently deal with a variety of issues that may hinder their capacity to provide teaching and promote student learning. The key informants of the study employed strategies to address the challenges they faced.

One major theme found in the study is the strategies for planning the lesson. Teacher A1 stated *“Napaka importante po na finafamiliarize po natin yung curriculum guide (CG) at nirereview po natin if align po ba talaga si topic sa ating CG”* Teacher B4 stated *“para po hindi ako maligaw at para po nakakasunod po ako even na may mga araw po na walang pasok, una po talaga titignan ko po yung budget of work at curriculum guide.”* Aside from teacher B4 and teacher A1’s statement, Teacher A3 stated that they allotted admin time to revisit the curriculum guide to foster changes in some activities so that the students can easily grasp understanding. These verbatim from the key informants encompass the sub-theme consulting curriculum guide as part of the strategies in lesson planning.

Consulting the curriculum guide leads the key informants to formulate supplementary activities and references in addressing the learning gap of the students. As stated by Teacher A5 *“Kasi alam mo kaya naman nating ma address yung learning gap eh, halimbawa nakakapag gawa tayo diba ng mga activities, additional readings, pati nag aadapt tayo ng change by updating our resources eh dapat hindi tayo nag ii-stay sa iisang book.”* this verbatim is supported by the verbatim of Teacher B1, stating *“Ayun po need po talaga natin i-revisit si curriculum guide para ma-update po talaga natin yung kakulangan ng mga estudyante kagaya po ng pag wawatch-to-learn po natin, tapos po activities po para ma measure po natin yung HOTS nila.”* These coded

verbatim formulated a sub-theme supplementary activities and references. The statement of the key informants is aligned to the study of Remillard (2005), which highlights the dynamic relationship between teachers and curricular features, emphasizing the need for teachers to construct responsive curriculum while adhering to the structure outlined in the curriculum guide. This tension underscores the significance of consulting the guide to strike a balance between flexibility and adherence to the curriculum.

The formulated sub-themes, consulting curriculum guide and supplementary activities and references encompass the major theme of strategies in lesson planning. Since teachers utilize strategies in lesson planning, teachers adjust their pedagogical approach. It is shown in the verbatim of Teacher B2 stating *“ako po nag aadjust ako depending on the strand na tinuturuuan ko po for example sa STEM since na observe ko po na mabilis silang mag catch-up medyo advance po ang set-up ng teaching and ni-lelevel ko po yung activities based sa kung pano po nila napaprocess yung lesson.”* this verbatim is supported by Teacher A5 *“Ako naman sir inaadjust ko yung art of questioning ko pagdating sa mga bata na nahihirapan magcatch-up para po maintindihan nila yung lesson”*. The narrative of the key informants is align with the assumption that teachers employ innovative strategies in addressing various student needs. The narrative of the key informants contributed to the major theme Adjustment of Approaches. It is crucial for teachers to adjust their approaches in education to meet the evolving needs of students and the changing educational landscape. The narrative stated are aligned with the assumptions that teachers adjust their lesson to address diversity of learners, student behavior and attitudes. Research has shown that the impact of training on university teachers' teaching skills and their approach to teaching can lead to changes in student learning approaches (Gibbs & Coffey, 2004).

With the different strategies in the pedagogical approach and strategies in lesson planning, teachers utilized criteria and motivate students to achieve learning success. As stated by Teacher A5 *“Para magkafeedback si students `nagbibigay kami ng rubric para guided sila sa mga sinusukat na criteria lalo na po sa essay writing. Doon sa criteria na yon nakakapag bigay tayo ng constructive feedback.”* This verbatim of Teacher A5 is supported by Teacher A3 *“Sa pag gawa po natin ng activity diba nga kailangan align yung activity sa lesson tapos may criteria ka na sinusunod.”* Teacher B1 added *“Sakin po kasi ineensure ko na malalaman agad ng bata yung scores nila so pinapakita ko po kung pano sila gine-gradan”*. These verbatim of the key informants contributed to the major theme ensuring that the students achieve performance indicators. Research has shown that rubrics make expectations explicit for students and that students do use rubrics for this purpose (Brookhart, 2018). Moreover, practicing rubric-referenced self-assessment has been found to enhance student performance on assignments (He & Canty, 2012).

By employing the strategies, teachers ensure that they provide quality education and support their students in achieving learning outcomes.

Table 1:
Student Agreement towards Teachers' Lesson Planning

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. I can finish my activities since my teacher used readily available learning materials (books, modules)	5.03	0.46	SOMEWHAT AGREE
2. I perform best on my activities because my teacher enumerates our learning objectives.	5.02	0.49	SOMEWHAT AGREE
3. I effectively understand the lesson when the teacher use different strategies to deliver the topic.	5.54	0.47	AGREE
4. I learn of the topic when the teacher engage students during the discussion.	5.48	0.58	AGREE
5. I easily understand the lesson when the teacher connects the lesson to my background, skills, and interest.	5.33	0.58	AGREE
6. I can accomplish activities when my teachers designate an activity that is aligned to my background, skills, and interest.	5.23	0.63	SOMEWHAT AGREE
7. I can accomplish assigned activities since my teacher requires available resources around me to finish it.	5.22	0.47	SOMEWHAT AGREE
8. I can understand the lesson when my teacher delivers the lesson with clear flow.	5.57	0.57	AGREE
9. I can understand and finish my activities because my teacher explains clear assessment criteria and standards that I can follow.	5.35	0.53	AGREE
10. I understand the discussion when the pacing of the lesson allows me to reflect and generalize the topic.	5.36	0.63	AGREE
COMPOSITE MEAN	5.31	0.54	AGREE

The Table No. 1, which shows that question number 8, I can understand the lesson when my teacher delivers the lesson with clear flow, obtained the highest rating among the given questions with a mean of 5.57 and a verbal interpretation of “agree”. On the other hand question number 2, I perform best on my activities because my teacher enumerates our learning objectives, obtained the lowest rating among the given questions with a mean of 5.02 and a verbal interpretation of “Somewhat Agree”. Overall, the questionnaires about the pedagogical content knowledge of teachers in terms of lesson planning obtained a grand weighted mean of 5.31, with a verbal interpretation of “agree.”

Table 2.
Student Agreement towards Teachers' Implementation

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. I understand the lesson because my teacher express clear communication of content.	5.24	0.63	SOMEWHAT AGREE
2. I understand the lesson when my teacher use clear and expressive written communication of content (if necessary)	5.31	0.55	AGREE
3. I clearly understand the topic when my teacher asks interesting question during instruction.	5.14	0.45	SOMEWHAT AGREE
4. Different instructional strategy of my teachers meets my learning needs during instruction.	5.24	0.51	SOMEWHAT AGREE
5. I gain understanding of the lesson when my teachers encourage us to contribute in the content, materials, and activities.	5.24	0.50	SOMEWHAT AGREE
6. I can easily accomplish my activities when my teacher discuss assessment criteria and standards to meet.	5.45	0.53	AGREE
7. I can clearly understand the lesson when my teacher makes adjustments of the lesson, if necessary.	5.42	0.69	AGREE
COMPOSITE MEAN	5.29	0.55	SOMEWHAT AGREE

The Table No. 2, which reveals that for question number 6, I can easily accomplish my activities when my teacher discusses the assessment criteria and standards to meet, obtained the highest rating among the given questions, with a mean of 5.45 and a verbal interpretation of "agree". On the other hand, the lowest rating falls under question number 3, I clearly understand the topic when my teacher asks an interesting question during discussion, with a mean of 5.14 and a verbal interpretation of "somewhat agree". Overall, the pedagogical content knowledge of teachers in terms of implementation obtained a grand weighted mean of 5.29, with a verbal interpretation of "somewhat agree".

Table 3.
Student Agreement towards Teachers' Feedback

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. I gain clarification of the topic when my teacher express verbal feedback towards my performance.	5.10	0.73	SOMEWHAT AGREE
2. I can improve my work when my teacher indicate score in my work as a form of feedback.	5.13	0.78	SOMEWHAT AGREE
3. I understand what to improve when my teacher indicate his/her suggestion with my performance	5.36	0.81	AGREE

4. I understand what to improve when my teacher underlines, circles, and provide a correct answer on my written work	5.24	0.92	SOMEWHAT AGREE
5. I perform better when my teacher wrote a comment that praises my written work.	5.27	0.77	SOMEWHAT AGREE
6. I improve my performance when my teacher relay timely feedback.	5.21	0.66	SOMEWHAT AGREE
7. I improve my performance when my teacher provide consistent and high quality feedback.	5.21	0.92	SOMEWHAT AGREE
COMPOSITE MEAN	5.22	0.60	SOMEWHAT AGREE

The Table no. 3, which exhibits that for question number 5, I performed better when my teacher wrote a comment that praised my written work and obtained the highest rating among the given questions, with a mean of 5.27 and a verbal interpretation of “somewhat agree”. On the other hand, in question number 1, I gain clarification of the topic when my teacher expressed verbal feedback towards my performance, obtained the lowest rating, with a mean of 5.10 and a verbal interpretation of “somewhat agree.” Overall, the pedagogical content knowledge of teachers in terms of feedback obtained a grand weighted mean of 5.22, with a verbal interpretation of “somewhat agree”

DISCUSSION

The pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) of a teacher has an important role in addressing quality education. PCK is considered a critical element in improving teaching quality and student learning outcomes (Evens et al., 2015). This is why it is important to identify and recognize existing challenges that may affect the development of PCK among educators. In order to realign and provide essential training that can help improve teachers' strategies for handling those challenges and fully develop their PCK level to promote effective teaching and learning processes, recognizing challenges in PCK among educators is essential for improving instructional quality and student progress. Studies have shown that PCK is distinguishable from teachers' content knowledge and is highly predictively valid for instructional quality, cognitive activation, and individual learning support (Krauss et al., 2020; Lucenario et al., 2016). It is supported by the statement that the development of PCK is crucial for fostering teacher competence, enhancing learning outcomes, and shaping the experiences of student teachers, ultimately impacting the quality of education (Ayoubi et al., 2017).

The data gathered through focus group discussions and narrative analysis was used to identify leading challenges that affect teachers' levels of PCK, as well as their strategies for addressing these challenges to deliver effective teaching instruction and help students achieve their learning outcomes. The teachers all indicated that they faced difficulty in lesson planning with regard to aligning learning objectives and developing learning activities because of the learners' diversity. As stated by Chaw & Tang (2023), understanding the characteristics and demographics of learners is crucial in designing learning environments that support and engage learners to enhance their overall learning

experience and performance. To address the problem, teachers revisit the curriculum guide to create adjustments that will cater to the needs of the learners. It emphasizes the significance of curriculum guide consultation as a strategy to enhance teachers' abilities to develop an effective lesson plan (Ndimbo & Kessy, 2023). On top of that, curriculum guides serve as guiding documents that direct teachers in the development of classroom activities aligned with educational standards and learning objectives (Gu, 2013).

Furthermore, the incidence of subject mismatch among teachers and time constraints in discussing topics budgeted for a specific semester provided a barrier, resulting in a learning gap for students. Moore et al. highlighted that many teachers already have gaps in their content knowledge within their own subjects, and expecting them to be familiar with other subjects can create further knowledge gaps (Shernoff et al., 2017). Also, the alignment between teachers and their primary subject significantly impacts student achievement, and teaching effectiveness found that teacher preparation and quality have a substantial effect on student achievement (Boyd et al., 2009). On the other hand, time constraints due to a compressed school calendar and the occurrence of unforeseen circumstances affecting school hours exacerbate the presence of learning gaps among students. As mentioned by Alexander et al. (2021), the impact of a fundamental design flaw in school improvement efforts, emphasizing the assumption that learning can be doled out by the clock and defined by the calendar, suggests that a compressed school calendar may limit flexibility to address the individual needs of students, potentially leading to academic inequality and learning disparities.

Teachers made an effort to bridge the learning gaps and addressed the challenges by revisiting the curriculum guide to make sure that content and instruction would be able to meet the competencies required for the specific subject. According to Meij & Marx (2018), it is important to make the curriculum visible to the students as it helps them activate prior knowledge and organize new knowledge into a meaningful context. This visibility can aid in addressing learning gaps by providing students with a clear understanding of the learning trajectory. Aside from that, utilizing multiple resources provides supplementary materials that help teachers deliver a concise and quality lesson despite having a compressed schedule. A study by Zheng (2022) highlighted the significance of high-quality teaching resources in improving teaching quality and educational development potential, emphasizing the role of resources in enhancing the overall learning environment.

Based on the study of Gupta et al. (2021), he emphasized the role of feedback in enhancing students' understanding of topics, retention, and overall learning effectiveness. It highlights the importance of incorporating feedback into teaching instruction to guide students and improve their learning comprehension. However, it is also a challenge among teachers to provide constructive feedback to the students without being perceived as a negative comment. In order for teachers to avoid bias and provide proper feedback, they used rubrics and ensured the immediate release of assessment scores to inform students about their performance. The rubrics provide clear relations between learning outcomes, activities, and assessment, underscoring the importance of them in guiding feedback and assessment aligned with learning goals (Dirkx et al., 2019).

The challenges encountered by the teachers and the strategies employed to address challenges is anchored to the Theory of Sustained Optimal Development in Teaching and Learning (Ahmed, 2017). This theory demonstrates that during teaching and learning, pacing and content difficulty levels are continuously adjusted. This theory aligns the expectations of instructors with students' abilities and inabilities, which promotes student learning and reduces the variation in student learning. After thorough data analysis, the researchers inferred that Senior High School Teachers experience challenges in teaching. Most of these challenges are external factors surrounding their content delivery to their students. However, it is noteworthy to emphasize that despite adversity, teachers employ several strategies to overcome the challenges they experience. Students' agreement with the survey sustains this integral result with their evaluation of teachers' pedagogical content knowledge in Lesson Planning, Lesson Implementation, and Feedback.

Conclusions

The findings of this study shed light on the challenges faced by Senior High School Teachers in their teaching practice, predominantly attributed to external factors impacting content delivery to students. However, amidst these challenges, it is evident that teachers demonstrate resilience and resourcefulness by employing various strategies to navigate and overcome obstacles. This resilience is further supported by students' feedback, which underscores the importance of teachers' pedagogical content knowledge in areas such as Lesson Planning, Implementation, and Feedback. These insights highlight the dynamic interplay between teacher challenges, strategies, and student perceptions, emphasizing the ongoing dedication and adaptability of educators in ensuring effective teaching and learning experiences despite the prevailing adversities.

Recommendations

The researchers recommend conducting this type of research in a wide range of locality to provide valuable data in teachers' challenges in different settings with an emphasis on expanding the number of possible key informants to provide rich narratives of teacher's experiences. In addition, the researchers also suggest allocating time and resources in the conduct of the proposed Organizational and Professional Development Plans especially in Private Educational Institutions.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

A great deal of attention was paid to ethical considerations during the conduct of this research, ensuring the protection and rights of all participants. Informed consent was obtained from each participant prior to any data collection, explaining the purpose of the study, procedures, and potential risks. Participants were assured of the right to withdraw at any time without consequence. Confidentiality measures were strictly observed throughout the research process, including data stored in a strictly encrypted online archive accessed only by authorized staff members who were reassured to the

respondents to remain anonymous and removed identifying clues from transcripts and reports to protect their privacy. Data privacy law were strictly observed, and only necessary data were collected to fulfill research objectives, minimizing any risk of data breach or unauthorized access. Such ethics this proposal confirms our commitment to integrity and the highest level of respect for the rights of our participants.

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